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“WATER FOR POOR MEN'S QUENCH”

A sneak from the memoirs of the barricade and the rosary
Blood extremely corpuscular injected through its ammunition
Against the water serenely reserved
Entailed through its placid, stagnant submission

Two weapons merged in one, eyes yielded to be blind
A silence in each gap
A pause or period with all its might
History held to be forgiven and so the present driven enliven

Thirteen years later, the long wait's over
A thin line of suspended hungry land
Poorly inhabited niche of thirst for water to blood
For breath of scent of nonchalant hand

Panting, even a drop, exhausted with no more to give
A white infinite strike with no more limit
The soul of pillars of twinge yet remaining sanity
Creeps for elongation an escape for damnation

No knowledge of universe, time and all
Satisfies with scrap of colossal establishments
A suffering ignorance from bliss to aghast
T'was shabby on outskirts behind the limelight

Then a knock so furious on the wall of the skin
Of the crocodile that swims around its rim
Deliberate attack on the conscience of the sorrowed pin
To the hearty grievous and rampant lying

Of Judas who uttered, "Why wasn't this perfume sold for silver coins?
And the money given to the poor?"
Jesus said, "You will always have poor people with you,

but you will not always have me."

The Calvary of the impoverished carried with thorns
Had delivered in front of the jury adjourned
And when the impetus of criminal adjuncts
The offense has laid to the peasants and the lads.

Then a little voice burst with anguish
Take our manna back which Israel accomplished
But the grievous shut its heaven beckon
Of cult with tremendous thunder of rocks!

Soon the descendants would pay for the hideous debts
And the mourning wouldn't strain the inconsiderate threats
The rain outbursts the soaked figure of larceny
To a complete recovery of the needy body

Then a mind progresses for the multitude
Of myriad ways to suck the manna from its origination
The recurring insipid loss flowed out
To anoint the deemed to be disturbed nation

And the dawn outbreaks its lamenting
Cover all thirty pieces of silver buried
From afar, praises are heard
All hail! A final quench from long-lived thirst!